

Prevalence of Obstructive Sleep Apnea in Hypertension Clinic Attendees of a Tertiary Care Centre

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ABSTRACT

Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA) and essential hypertension (HT) are common conditions affecting middle-aged and elderly adults. This study was done to know the percentage of hypertensive patients having Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA) and to correlate severity of OSA with the severity of hypertension. Fifty hypertensive patients attending hypertension clinic of People's Hospital enrolled as per inclusion criteria were subjected to detailed history, general examination, blood pressure measurements and overnight Polysomnography (PSG). Apart from this, clinical data gathered was applied to Sleep Questionnaires- Berlin Questionnaire, STOP-Bang Questionnaire, and NoSAS score. Mild and severe obstructive sleep apnea was found in 12% of patients each, whereas moderate obstructive sleep apnea was seen in only 6% of patients. 11 patients with stage I hypertension and 24 patients with stage II hypertension did not have OSA. Patients with stage I hypertension had mild OSA. Patients with stage II hypertension had all severity of OSA but there were more patients with severe OSA (6) than mild OSA (3) or moderate OSA (3). Only a minority of patients (30%) with essential hypertension had OSA. Majority of the patients with stage I and stage II hypertension did not have OSA. Severity of OSA increased with the increase in stage of hypertension but the observed correlation was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$)

KEY WORDS: essential hypertension, NoSAS, obstructive sleep apnea, sensitivity

INTRODUCTION:

Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA) and essential hypertension (HT) are common conditions affecting middle-aged and elderly adults. The highest level of epidemiologic evidence supports the association between OSA and HT.^[1,2]

Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA) is the most common form of sleep-disordered breathing.^[3] It is a challenge for the healthcare system due to its high prevalence in the adult population and its linked morbidity and mortality (e.g., traffic accidents and cardiovascular complications).^[4,5] Observational studies have shown that the prevalence of OSA is around 30% in hypertensive patients and nearly 80% in resistant hypertensive patients.^[6-9] Conversely, the reported prevalence of HT in those with OSA ranged from 15 to 56%.^[10]

We hypothesized that in people having essential hypertension, some might have OSA,

previously undiagnosed due to lack of symptoms or may not have been diagnosed by consulting physician. This study was conducted to assess percentage of hypertensive patients having Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA) and to correlate severity of OSA with the severity of hypertension.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In a unicentric observational study done during January 2018 to June 2019, 264 hypertensive patients attended hypertension clinic of tertiary care hospital, at Bhanpur area of Bhopal. They were explained about the study protocol and sleep study. Only 90 patients consented for the study and these were enrolled. Forty out of 90 patients who had associated conditions like symptomatic heart failure, neuromuscular disease, known diagnosis of COPD or Asthma, hypoxemia were excluded. Thus, 50 hypertensive patients were subjected to PSG for the diagnosis of OSA. The inclusion criteria of the study was age >18 years, known case of hypertension and patients consenting for the study.

Detailed information regarding socio demographic variables such as age, gender and occupation were recorded and entered in questionnaire. All subjects were enquired about a history of HT, medications used, and other medical

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conditions. General examination of patients was done. Height, BMI, neck circumference, and waist circumference were measured using an inextensible tape. Blood pressure measurement (in mm of Hg) was recorded and classified according to the Joint National Committee (JNC)-7 criteria. Apart from this, detailed clinical history was taken and clinical data gathered was applied in Sleep Questionnaires- Berlin Questionnaire, STOP-Bang Questionnaire, and NoSAS score.

Fifty eligible patients were subjected to overnight polysomnography (using Philips Alice-6 Diagnostic System) for the detection of OSA. Raw data obtained was manually scored in 30-second epochs for sleep staging using the American Academy of Sleep Medicine (2012) criteria.^[11] OSA was defined by the presence of apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) 5 or greater. Patients were classified either as normal (AHI < 5/h), mild (AHI $\geq$ 5 and <15), moderate (AHI $\geq$ 15 and <30), or severe (AHI $\geq$ 30).

Data was compiled using MS Excel and analyzed using IBM SPSS software version 20. Frequency and percentage were calculated & statistical test (Chi-Square) was applied wherever applicable; $p < 0.05$ was taken as statically significant and $p < 0.01$ was taken highly significant. Sensitivity and specificity were calculated for a sleep questionnaire against AHI and expressed as a percentage and compared using the ROC curve.

RESULTS:

Fifty hypertensive patients were recruited for the study. Mean age of patients was 50 years. Majority of the patients i.e. 74% were males. Maximum number of patients were obese. Grade 1, grade 2 and grade 3 obesity were observed in 34%, 32%, and 8% patients respectively. Demographic data and Baseline characteristics of hypertensive patients are depicted herein (Table 1).

Our study included the hypertensive patients. Majority of the patients were stage II hypertensives (72%) and Stage I hypertension was observed in 28% of the patients. Maximum number of the hypertensive patients did not have Obstructive Sleep Apnea. Mild (AHI $\geq$ 5 - <15) and severe (AHI $\geq$ 30) obstructive sleep apnea was found in 12% of patients each. Moderate obstructive sleep apnea (AHI $\geq$ 15 - <30) was seen in only 6% of patients. Majority of the patients with stage I and stage II hypertension did not have OSA. Patients with stage I hypertension had mild OSA. In Patients with stage II hypertension, severe OSA was more common than was found in mild or

moderate OSA. No significant association was found between hypertension and OSA ($p > 0.05$). (Table 2)

Our study observed positive correlation between severity of hypertension and AHI i.e. as the stage of hypertension increased, AHI also increased but the observed correlation was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). (Table 3) PSG diagnosed OSA in 15 patients. Berlin, Stop Bang and NoSAS identified 10, 12 and 9 patients respectively as high risk for OSA. Similarly out of 35 patients diagnosed with no OSA by PSG, no risk for OSA was observed in 29 cases each with all the questionnaires. Most sensitive questionnaire for diagnosis of OSA was STOP-Bang (80%) followed by Berlin (66.7%) and NoSAS (60%). Similarly, specificity, PPV as well as NPV were also high for STOP Bang questionnaire as compared to other two questionnaire. Area under curve was maximum for STOP Bang questionnaire (0.81). (Table 4)

DISCUSSION:

In our study, 50 hypertensive patients having mild, moderate or severe HTN underwent Polysomnography. OSA was found in only 30% of the patients. In 15-18 patients detected to be at high risk for OSA by the three questionnaires, OSA was confirmed by PSG in 60-80% of the patients. This reinforces that all hypertensives need not undergo PSG. Only those classified as high risk for OSA by any of the three questionnaires – Berlin, STOP-Bang and NoSAS should undergo PSG. Twenty eight percent of our patients had stage I hypertension, 72% had stage II hypertension. There were no patients with resistant hypertension in our study.

Majority of the patients with stage I hypertension did not have OSA (78.6%). Only 21.4% patients who had stage I hypertension had OSA, which was mild. Similarly, majority of the patients with stage II hypertension did not have OSA (66.7%) but there were higher number of patients with severe OSA (16.7%) than mild and moderate OSA (8.3% and 8.3% each) in this group. Stage II hypertensive patients had higher number of patients with OSA as compared to patients with stage I hypertension, but no association was found between stage of HTN and presence of OSA ($p > 0.05$). We observed that severity of OSA is not related to the severity of HTN.

Epidemiologic evidence supports the association between OSA and HT. OSA is one of the underlying relevant treatable factors associated with hypertension.^[1,2] Previous studies have demonstrated the occurrence of hypertension in patients with Sleep apnea. However, the present study is unique as we

Table 1: Demographic data and Baseline characteristics of hypertensive patients (n=50).

Baseline Variables		Frequency (n=50)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (years)	<35	4	8
	35-44	10	20
	45-54	19	38
	55-64	11	22
	≥65	6	12
Gender	Male	37	74
	Female	13	26
BMI		Frequency (n=50)	Percentage (%)
Underweight (<18)		2	4
Normal (18-22.4)		2	4
Overweight (22.5-24.9)		9	18
Grade 1 obese (25-29.9)		17	34
Grade 2 obese (30-39.9)		16	32
Grade 3 obese (≥40)		4	8

Table 2: Association of OSA with hypertension.

OSA	Hypertension	
	Stage I n (%), 14(28 %)	Stage II n (%), 36(72%)
None	11 (78.6)	24 (66.7)
Mild (AHI =5 - <15) (12%)	3 (21.4)	3 (8.3)
Moderate(AHI=15-<30)(6%)	0 (0)	3 (8.3)
Severe (≥30) (12%)	0 (0)	6 (16.7)
Chi Square (?2)=95.12, p=0.16		

Table 3: Correlation of Stage of hypertension with AHI.

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	SE of Estimate	F	Sig.
0.205	0.042	0.022	26.821	2.111	0.153

have tried to determine the occurrence of OSA in hypertensive patients. The mean age of hypertensive patients was 50.34±11.39 years and majority of the patients (74 %) were obese in our study. Grade 1, grade 2 and grade 3 obesity was observed in 34%, 32%, and 8% hypertensive patients respectively. Studies in the past have already established that hypertension and OSA are associated with obesity.^[12,13]

In 168 hypertensive patients studied by Borsini E et al, there were more patients with mild OSA(40.5%), than with moderate (23.8%) and severe OSA(20.2%). In contrast to our study, high prevalence of OSA in hypertensive patients was found by Borsini E et al as they performed PSG only in those hypertensive who had high risk for OSA as screened by ESS and STOP-Bang questionnaire.^[14] Fletcher EC

Table 4: Diagnostic accuracy of sleep questionnaire.

	Sleep questionnaire		
	Berlin, n (%)	STOP-Bang, n (%)	NoSAS, n (%)
Proportion of high risk	16 (32.0)	18 (36.0)	15 (30.0)
OSA confirmed by PSG	30%		
Sensitivity	66.7	80	60
Specificity	82.9	82.9	82.9
PPV	62.5	66.7	60
NPV	85.3	90.6	82.9
AUC	0.75	0.81	0.71

et al studied 46 hypertensives and 34 normotensive-patients to know the proportion of patients having OSA. All patients underwent polysomnography. Proportion of hypertensive patients having OSA was similar to our study (30%). Disordered breathing events per hour were significantly higher in hypertensive patients (18.1) as compared to the normotensive controls (8.9) and the observed difference was statistically highly significant ($p < 0.002$).^[9] Udwardia et al conducted two-phase cross-sectional prevalence study and 250 patients underwent an overnight home sleep study. The estimated prevalence of SDB (apnea-hypopnea index of 5 or more) was 19.5%.^[15] Borgel J et al evaluated hypertensives for unrecognized secondary causes of HTN. OSA was found in 70.8% of the screened patients.^[16]

In our study, Berlin, STOP-Bang, and NoSAS scoring systems were used to assess the risk of OSA. Maximum patients with high risk of OSA were identified by the STOP-Bang questionnaire (18) followed by Berlin questionnaire (16) and NoSAS score (15). We compared the risk assessment of OSA among various questionnaires to confirm and compare their diagnostic validity. Out of 18 patients detected to have high risk of OSA by the STOP-Bang questionnaire, PSG detected OSA in 12 patients. Those at high risk of OSA by Berlin questionnaire (16 patients) and NoSAS score (15 patients), PSG detected OSA in 10 patients and 9 patients respectively. The sensitivity was highest (80%) for STOP-Bang questionnaire and lowest (60%) for NoSAS score. The specificity was similar for all three questionnaires (82.9%). NPV and PPV were highest for the STOP-Bang questionnaire. The diagnostic accuracy of various questionnaires was assessed using the Receiver Operating curve (ROC). The area under the

curve measures discrimination, that is, the ability of the test to correctly classify those with and without the disease or at high risk for the disease. The area under curve was highest for the STOP-Bang questionnaire i.e. (0.81) followed by the Berlin questionnaires and NoSAS score.

Talarowska P et al in their study observed that maximum number of high risk for OSA was identified by the NoSAS score (63.7%) followed by Berlin (41%) and STOP-Bang questionnaires (33.9%).^[17] Tan A et al found that all three questionnaires performed similarly regardless of AHI cutoff values. The AUCs clustered around 0.692–0.738 and 0.682–0.748 for AHI ≥ 20 and 30 events, respectively i.e. there were no differences in performance between the three questionnaires.^[18] Tan A et al suggested that these questionnaires should be used only as screening tools to rule out low-risk subjects for severe OSA. Subjects who are identified as high risk via these questionnaires will still require further confirmation by PSG.^[18]

The Berlin questionnaire takes a longer time to fill but the interpretation is simple. The scoring of the STOP-Bang questionnaire is simple and it was observed to be more sensitive than other questionnaires. The NoSAS score is slightly more complicated as it has a differential scoring system for each variable, but it is the easiest to fill. All the questionnaires can be used as a screening tool for identification of OSA but the best screening tool to diagnose the presence of OSA i.e. mild, moderate as well as severe OSA, was STOP-Bang questionnaire.

CONCLUSION:

Only a minority of patients (30%) with essential hypertension had OSA. Our study showed that all patients with essential hypertension do not

require PSG. Hypertensive patients should first be screened by any of the three questionnaires Berlin questionnaire, STOP-Bang questionnaire, or NoSAS score. Those found to be at high risk for OSA by questionnaires should be subjected to polysomno-graphy to rule out OSA. Patients with stage I hypertension had mild OSA. More patients with stage II hypertension had severe OSA than moderate and mild OSA.

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